

“MOBILE LEARNING AND ITS IMPACT ON ENGLISH VOCABULARY DEVELOPMENT”

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Annotation. *This article examines the role of mobile learning (m-learning) in vocabulary development in English language learning. With the rapid introduction of digital technologies in education, mobile devices have become a convenient and effective tool for language learning. The study analyzes how applications such as “Duolingo”, “Quizlet”, “Ibart academy” and “Memrise” promote vocabulary retention, motivation, and student independence. The results show that m-learning creates a flexible and interactive environment that enhances vocabulary knowledge through repetition, game elements, and contextual practice. The article also discusses the advantages and limitations of m-learning for vocabulary development.*

Key words: mobile, vocabulary, education, autonomy.

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается роль мобильного обучения (m-learning) в развитии словарного запаса при изучении английского языка. Благодаря быстрому внедрению цифровых технологий в образование мобильные устройства стали удобным и эффективным инструментом для изучения языка. В исследовании анализируются, как такие приложения, как “Duolingo”, “Quizlet”, “Ibrat academy” и “Memrise”, способствуют сохранению словарного запаса, мотивации и самостоятельности учащихся. Результаты показывают, что мобильное обучение создаёт гибкую и интерактивную среду, которая расширяет словарный запас посредством повторения, игровых элементов и контекстной практики. В статье также обсуждаются преимущества и ограничения мобильного обучения для развития словарного запаса.*

Ключевые слова: мобильный, словарный запас, обучение, автономность.

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o‘rganishda mobil o‘qitishning (m-learning) so‘z boyligini rivojlantirishdagi roli ko‘rib chiqiladi. Ta‘limda raqamli texnologiyalarning tez joriy etilishi bilan mobil qurilmalar til o‘rganish uchun qulay va samarali vositaga aylandi. Tadqiqotda “Duolingo”, “Quizlet”, “Ibrat academy” va “Memrise” kabi ilovalar so‘z boyligini saqlash, motivatsiya va o‘quvchining mustaqilligini qanday rag‘batlantirishi tahlil qilinadi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, m-learning takrorlash, o‘yin elementlari va kontekstual amaliyot orqali so‘z boyligini oshiradigan moslashuvchan va interaktiv muhit yaratadi. Maqolada shuningdek, so‘z boyligini rivojlantirish uchun m-learning afzalliklari va cheklovlari muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: mobil, o‘qitish, so‘z boyligi, mustaqillik.

Introduction. It is universally accepted that, mobile learning is learning using mobile phones, tablets or other portable devices. It allows you to study anywhere and anytime - at home, on the bus or even in the park. This type of learning is very popular now because people use phones every day and it is easy to install useful English learning apps on them. We know that,

with mobile learning, students can watch videos, play educational games, read texts and learn new words. This helps them memorize vocabulary faster and makes the learning process more interesting and convenient, as they can learn at their own pace.

In currently, the mobile learning is widely used for improving English skills, such as vocabulary development, grammar practice and some how help to communication skills. As Traxler notes, “Mobile learning represents learning that happens across locations, times and contexts through the use of personal, portable devices” [1;1-12]. It means that, we can use this devices, like “Duolingo”, “Quizlet”, “Ibrat academy” and “Memrise” anywhere, like at home or in outsides it does not matter.

The role of mobile applications in vocabulary development. Many people opine that, mobile applications such as “Duolingo”, “Quizlet”, “Ibrat academy” and “Memrise” make the English learning process more interactive and enjoyable. By the way, these devices create comforts and some of them are free, which means we can study effectively and for free without losing money. Each of these application uses in different techniques for improving vocabulary skills. For instance:

	Function	Helps with
Duolingo	Teaches foreign languages through interactive and game-based activities (reading, listening, translating, pronunciation).	Helps improve vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation.
Quizlet	Allows users to create and study flashcards, play educational games, and test their knowledge.	Helps learn and remember new words and concepts quickly.
Ibrat academy	An online platform for learning foreign languages and preparing for IELTS and CEFR exams	Helps prepare for international exams and improve overall language skills.
Memrise	It uses videos and repetition to teach real-life language and pronunciation by native and professional speakers.	Helps understand real speech and expand vocabulary.

As Godwin-Jones points out, “mobile learning helps to increase vocabulary by providing continuous contact with target words through engaging digital content” [2; 2-12]

In these years, we can show the mobile learning increasing day by day, especially it began increase after global issue, like pandemic “Covid-19”. As was said in statistics last year “This has accelerated the market growth and encouraged institutions and businesses to widely adopt mobile learning solutions. The market is expected to have a solid base value by 2025 and lay the foundation for sustainable expansion until 2033” [4]

Picture1. <https://www.futuremarketreport.com/ru/industry-report/mobile-learning-market>.

In addition this statistic is rising rapidly in our country, there is a great need for free and effective training devices and there are many students, who use these devices and learn English or other languages.

Limitations and difficulties. However, despite its advantages, mobile learning also has some limitations. Sometimes students can get distracted by entertainment content, and they can also struggle with poor internet connections. In addition, not everyone has the self-discipline to study independently. Although, as Kukulska-Hulm and Schild point out, “the pedagogical potential of mobile learning depends on how well it is integrated into general educational practices” [3; 271-289]. This means that teachers need to help students effectively use mobile technologies to learn vocabulary. Besides, also have some difficulties of mobile learning, such as, small screen size, unequal access, distractions, technical issues and lack guidance.

Thence, we should combine mobile learning with traditional classroom methods to achieve the best results in the future. Sure, in some apps has these methods, but some people, who want to begin learning English do not know about this devices perhaps. This can be a little problem for new learners. I think that, we should pay attention to this, so that such troubles do not arise in the future.

Conclusion. In conclusion, I want to say that, the mobile learning plays a significant role in developing not only English vocabulary, but also it helps to develop our language skills. Mobile apps, such as, “Duolingo”, “Quizlet”, “Ibrat Academy” and “Memrise” can help students memorize vocabulary easily and stay motivated. However, for best results, mobile learning should be used in conjunction with teacher guidance and traditional lessons.

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